

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS DENOTING THE CONCEPT OF WISDOM

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Abstract: *This article provides information about phraseological units about the concept of “Wisdom”. The structural and stylistic classification of phraseological units have been mentioned based on the concept.*

Key words: *concept, phraseological units, structural classification, stylistic classification, lexeme, an intelligent person.*

Introduction. At the end of the XIX century, the Swiss researcher S. Bally proposed to distinguish collections of words in the language according to the degree of stability: free phrases that separate immediately after formation (red hair, red light, red toy; blue eyes, blue sky, blue book); familiar combinations characterized by relative freedom of components (fair complexion, dark complexion, sallow complexion, swarthy complexion); phraseological series, the stability of which is fixed by primary word usage (delicate ear – fine hearing, to pull a long face – to stretch out (about the face)), and phraseological units as indecomposable combinations, the components of which have lost their original meaning. At the same time, as the main sign of the integrity of phraseological unity, he called the possibility of its replacement by a word identifier.

Materials and Methods. It is Sh. Bally who is considered the founder of the theory of phraseological units, although his views have been widely discussed by many linguists (in particular, the mandatory presence of lexical synonyms in phraseological units).

According to the semantic classification, the largest number of phraseological units (12 phraseological units) are phraseological combinations. For example: *wise as Solomon* — clever, intelligent as Solomon, *to have a head on one's shoulders* - to have a head on your shoulders. The average number of phraseological units (9 phraseological units) is phraseological units. For example: *to have all one's buttons on-the pot cooks, to have one's feet on the ground* – to have common sense. The

smallest number of phraseological units (9 phraseological units) is phraseological splices. For example: *thinking mug* – head.

According to the structural classification of phraseological units with the meaning “Wise” we found the largest number of examples of verb-predicative (12 phraseological units). For example, *to have a good head on the shoulders* - to have a head on your shoulders, *to pick smb’s brains* - to use other people’s thoughts. The average number of phraseological units (10 phraseological units) we have found examples an adjectival comparison that coincides with the functions of an adjective. For example: *a clear head* - a bright head, a clear mind, *smart Aleck* - a smart guy, a know-it-all. We found the smallest number of examples with a construction with a subordinate union (2 phraseological units). For example: a *mind like a steel trap* is a tenacious mind.

According to the stylistic classification of phraseological units with the meaning “Wise”, we found the largest number of examples of colloquial phraseological turns (21 phraseological units). For example: *smart Aleck*- smart guy, know-it-all, *to have a good head on the shoulders* - to have a head on your shoulders, *pick smb’s to brains* - to use other people’s thoughts.

Results and Discussions. In many phraseological units, an intelligent person is represented in phraseological turns as a person with positive qualities. For example: *to have one’s feet on the ground* - to have common sense, to have a good head on the shoulders - to have a head on your shoulders. Presence an intelligent person makes life easier. For example, in phraseological units *wise as Solomon, as to have an old head on young shoulders* – to be smart beyond your years, drive home – to bring to mind, etc. the affirmative degree of mental state is emphasized. In turn, an intelligent person is compared with wisdom, comparing him with Solomon the Wise. Also, an intelligent person is characterized by his age. For example: *to have an old head on young shoulders* – to be smart is not by years. A large amount of knowledge and wise experience add years to a person. It is also worth noting that the names of body parts are often involved in the formation of phraseological units of the English language. The trunk, head, shoulders, legs are all parts of the body involved in phraseology.

For example: *a sound mind in a sound body* - a healthy mind in a healthy body, to have one’s feet on the ground - have common sense, to have a good head on the shoulders - to have a head on your shoulders. Torso it is compared with strength, with health, maintaining a healthy mind on yourself. Firmly standing feet on the ground are compared with common sense. Shoulders are compared with strength, with health, holding the head on itself. The head is compared with mental activity. Using the names of parts of speech in a figurative sense, a person tries to convey his thoughts and

emotions from what he said more deeply and more fully. The head is a kind of storage of the mind.

This lexeme is used in many phraseological units. Basically, the connotation of phraseological units is positive. For example: *be in one's right mind* (be of sound mind) - be in your right mind, *a clear head* - a bright head, a clear mind, *a word is enough to the wise* - a smart person understands half a word.

Conclusion. An intelligent person in these phraseological units is characterized with clarity, brightness, health and speed of understanding. There is also a negative connotation of phraseological units. For example: smart Aleck – arrogant, know-it-all, too clever by half - painfully smart, too smart. Negative connotation is characterized by the phrases denoting a person "extremely smart", who claims to have a high opinion of his intellectual abilities, who wants to show his intelligence and knowledge.

This phraseology is used for negative characterization. Basically, according to the method of formation of phraseological units of this concept.

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